

1 Title:

2 A single low-dimensional neural component of motor unit activity explains force generation
3 across repetitive isometric tasks

4
5 Authors:

6 Hélio V. Cabral¹, J. Greig Inglis¹, Elmira Pourreza¹, Milena A. Dos Santos¹, Caterina
7 Cosentino¹, David O'Reilly², Ioannis Delis², Francesco Negro¹

8
9 Affiliations:

10 ¹Department of Clinical and Experimental Sciences, Università degli Studi di Brescia, Brescia,
11 Italy

12 ²School of Biomedical Sciences, University of Leeds, West Yorkshire, UK

13
14 Acknowledgements:

15 This study was funded by the European Research Council Consolidator Grant INCEPTION
16 contract no. 101045605. J Greig Inglis was supported by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
17 Grant 'MUDecomp' agreement no. 101151712. Ioannis Delis was supported by the BBSRC
18 grant no. BB/Y513799/1.

19
20 Conflict of interest:

21 The authors declare no competing financial interests.

22
23 Corresponding author:

24 Prof. Francesco Negro

25 Department of Clinical and Experimental Sciences

26 Università degli Studi di Brescia

27 Viale Europa 11, Brescia, 25121, Italy

28 Tel: +39 0303717452

29 Email: francesco.negro@unibs.it

30 **Abstract**

31 Previous studies suggest that low-dimensional control underlies motor unit activity, with low-
32 frequency oscillations in common synaptic inputs serving as the primary determinant of muscle
33 force production. In this study, we used principal component analysis (PCA) and factor
34 analysis (FA) to investigate the relationship between low-dimensional motor unit components
35 and force oscillations during repetitive isometric tasks with similar force profiles. We assessed
36 the consistency of these components across trials in both individual (tibialis anterior; first
37 dorsal interosseous) and synergistic muscles (vastus medialis, VM; vastus lateralis, VL).
38 Participants performed 15 trials of a force-matching learning task. Three post-skill acquisition
39 trials were selected for analysis to ensure high similarity in force profiles. Motor units were
40 decomposed from high-density surface electromyograms, tracked across trials, and their
41 smoothed discharge rates were decomposed into low-dimensional components using PCA and
42 FA. Parallel analysis indicated that a single component could explain the smoothed discharge
43 rates for the individual muscles and two components for VM-VL. Importantly, the first
44 component explained most of the variance (~70%) in smoothed discharge rates across all
45 muscles. The first motor unit component also showed significantly higher correlations with
46 force oscillations than the second component and remained highly consistent across trials.
47 These findings were further supported by a non-linear framework combining network- and
48 information-theoretic tools, which revealed high motor unit network density in the first
49 component of all muscles. Collectively, these results suggest that, during isometric
50 contractions, motor unit activity is primarily controlled by a single dominant shared synaptic
51 input that closely mirrors force oscillations.

52

53 **Keywords:** force control; common synaptic input; HDsEMG; low-dimensional control;
54 dimensionality reduction; motor unit networks; latent variables.

55 **Introduction**

56 The central nervous system (CNS) generates and controls movement by transmitting and
57 modulating neural commands to muscles, ensuring precise coordination and force production
58 (Liddell and Sherrington, 1925; Sherrington, 1925). Although movement execution often
59 appears effortless, even simple and repetitive tasks, such as reaching or walking, involve
60 remarkable complexity. These actions require the simultaneous activation of multiple muscles,
61 each comprising thousands of motor units, to generate torque across multiple joints and
62 produce purposeful motion (Bernshteĭn, 1967; Lacquaniti et al., 2012; D'avella and Lacquaniti,
63 2013). At every level of the motor control hierarchy, the CNS must coordinate a vast number
64 of interacting elements while managing the hierarchical mismatch between their abundance
65 (e.g., much greater number of alpha motor neurons than the number of muscles). While this
66 redundancy in the neuromuscular system offers flexibility and adaptability, it also presents a
67 complex control problem, as the CNS must navigate infinite potential solutions to achieve a
68 given motor goal (commonly referred to as the "degrees of freedom problem"; Bernshteĭn
69 (1967)).

70 Several theoretical frameworks have addressed the degrees of freedom problem (Latash et al.,
71 2007; Bruton and O'Dwyer, 2018). Among them, a prominent hypothesis is that the CNS
72 employs a modular control strategy rather than individually controlling each element, reducing
73 the complexity and dimensionality of control (Tresch et al., 2002; Gentner and Classen, 2006;
74 Giszter et al., 2007; Bizzi et al., 2008; Tresch and Jarc, 2009; Alessandro et al., 2013; Ting et
75 al., 2015). One key formulation of this modular control is the muscle synergy hypothesis, which
76 proposes that a repertoire of movements is generated by the coordinated activity of muscles,
77 referred to as synergies, in weighted combinations (Tresch et al., 1999; d'Avella et al., 2003;
78 Ting and Macpherson, 2005). Empirical evidence supporting the existence of muscle synergies
79 has been gathered from both animal (Tresch et al., 1999; Saltiel et al., 2001; d'Avella et al.,

80 2003; Overduin et al., 2008) and human (Soechting and Lacquaniti, 1989; Ivanenko et al.,
81 2005; d'Avella et al., 2011) studies, where the observed muscle activity or kinematic patterns
82 were modeled as linear combinations of a small set of components (Tresch et al., 2006). Despite
83 its valuable contributions to understanding neuromuscular control, this body of research has
84 primarily analyzed the muscles rather than the individual motor units activating them.

85 Recent advances in technology and analytical methods have shifted the scale of analysis from
86 muscles to individual neurons. These developments have enabled the recording and analysis of
87 the activity of several motor neurons at both cortical (Kipke et al., 2008; Cunningham and Yu,
88 2014; Gao and Ganguli, 2015; Steinmetz et al., 2021) and spinal (Holobar and Zazula, 2007;
89 Muceli et al., 2015; Chen and Zhou, 2016; Negro et al., 2016b; Muceli et al., 2022) levels,
90 significantly advancing the understanding of the dimensionality of neural control. At the
91 cortical level, compelling evidence has shown that movement planning and execution are
92 governed by a small set of neural activity patterns spanning a low-dimensional space, often
93 referred to as the “neural manifold” (Gallego et al., 2017). Corroborating earlier research that
94 investigated the collective behavior of neurons (De N, 1938; Hebb, 1949), this evidence
95 supports the idea that the population, rather than single neuron, is the fundamental unit
96 underlying neural dynamics (Saxena and Cunningham, 2019; Ebitz and Hayden, 2021; Yuste
97 et al., 2024). A similar framework has been proposed at the spinal level, where examining the
98 pool of motor units offers deeper insights into muscle force control (Farina and Negro, 2015).
99 Simulation and experimental studies have extensively demonstrated that the alpha motor
100 neuron pool acts as a highly selective filter, linearly transmitting the common synaptic inputs
101 while attenuating independent inputs (Negro et al., 2009; Negro and Farina, 2011; Farina et al.,
102 2014; Negro et al., 2016a; Thompson et al., 2018). These findings suggest that common
103 synaptic inputs are the primary determinant of generated muscle force during isometric
104 contractions, supporting the hypothesis that low-dimensional neural control extends to motor

105 unit activity (Negro et al., 2009; Laine et al., 2015; Madarshahian et al., 2021; Del Vecchio et
106 al., 2023; Hug et al., 2023; Levine et al., 2023; Rossato et al., 2024).

107 A defining feature of low-dimensional neural control is the coupling among elements within
108 the system, which results in a high degree of correlation among neural outputs (De Luca et al.,
109 1982; Georgopoulos et al., 1982; Farmer et al., 1993; Hatsopoulos et al., 1998). Consequently,
110 dimensionality reduction techniques, such as principal component analysis (PCA) and factor
111 analysis (FA), have been widely applied to discharge rates of neuronal ensembles to identify
112 dominant patterns of covariation, yielding a reduced set of explanatory components that
113 capture key control features (Cunningham and Yu, 2014). For instance, Negro et al. (2009)
114 demonstrated that the first principal component, derived using PCA from the smoothed
115 discharge rates of active motor units, explains oscillations in isometric force more effectively
116 than the discharge rates of individual motor units. In general, there exists a strong justification
117 for using PCA to investigate patterns of neuronal correlation (Chapin and Nicolelis, 1999;
118 Negro et al., 2009; Churchland et al., 2010; Levine et al., 2023) since PCA is mathematically
119 linked to Hebbian theory (Oja, 1989, 1992; Olshausen, 1998), one of the most experimentally
120 validated theories of synaptic plasticity (Hebb, 1949). More recent studies using alternative
121 rotations of low-dimensional components or other dimensionality reduction techniques have
122 suggested that multiple components may underlie motor neuron activity, particularly when
123 synergistic muscles are involved (Del Vecchio et al., 2023; Nuccio et al., 2024; Rossato et al.,
124 2024). If low-dimensional control is indeed an effective strategy for simplifying neural control
125 via common projections to spinal motor neurons, the resulting components should closely
126 mirror force oscillations (i.e., the final motor output) and exhibit consistency across trials with
127 similar force outputs.

128 In this study, we investigated the relationship between low-dimensional components of motor
129 unit activity and oscillations in muscle force during repetitive isometric tasks with highly
130 similar force outputs. We further examined the consistency of these components across trials
131 both for individual (tibialis anterior, TA; first dorsal interosseous, FDI) and synergistic muscles
132 (vastus medialis, VM; vastus lateralis, VL). Participants performed fifteen trials of a force-
133 matching learning task, and, following the learning phase, three consecutive trials were
134 analyzed to ensure high similarity in force oscillations. Motor units were decomposed from
135 high-density surface electromyograms (HDsEMG), tracked across these trials, and their
136 smoothed discharge rates were linearly decomposed into low-dimensional components using
137 PCA and FA. To further characterize the coupling among motor unit activity across trials, we
138 employed a recently developed non-linear framework combining information and network
139 theoretic tools to decompose neural signals and characterize their network structure (O'Reilly
140 and Delis, 2022, 2024). We hypothesized that a single low-dimensional component, highly
141 resembling force oscillations, would show strong consistency across trials, regardless of the
142 muscle analyzed or method employed.

143 **Methods**

144 *Participants*

145 Twenty-nine healthy participants performed a series of isometric force-matching tasks
146 involving index finger abduction (FDI muscle), dorsiflexion (TA muscle), and knee extension
147 (VM-VL muscles). Specifically, ten volunteers (4 females; age 31 ± 4 years; height 177 ± 8
148 cm; mass 72 ± 17 kg) participated in the FDI experiments, twelve volunteers (5 females; mean
149 \pm SD: age 31 ± 3 years; height 175 ± 9 cm; mass 69 ± 18 kg) in the TA experiment, and seven
150 male volunteers (age 33 ± 10 years; height 184 ± 5 cm; mass 85 ± 19 kg) in the VM-VL
151 experiment. Seven volunteers participated in both the TA and FDI experiments in separate
152 sessions. All participants had no history of upper or lower limb injuries that could impact their
153 ability to perform voluntary contractions. Before beginning the experiments, participants
154 provided informed consent following an explanation of the experimental procedures. This
155 study was approved by the local ethics committee of the University of Brescia (code NP5665)
156 and conducted in accordance with the latest version of the Declaration of Helsinki.

157 *Experimental protocol*

158 **Figure 1** illustrates the participants' positioning for the index finger abduction, dorsiflexion,
159 and knee extension tasks. For the index finger abduction task, participants were seated with
160 their right wrist neutrally positioned on a custom-built device with their elbow flexed at 45° (0°
161 being fully extended). The index finger was secured to an adjustable support attached to a load
162 cell (SM-100 N, Interface, Arizona, USA) to record the isometric abduction force produced by
163 the index finger (**Figure 1A**). To minimize the involvement of other muscles, the wrist was
164 secured to the device with Velcro straps, and the other fingers (little, middle and ring) were
165 strapped separately from the index finger. The thumb was fixed to an adjustable support,
166 maintaining an approximate angle of 80° to the index finger (**Figure 1A**). For the dorsiflexion
167 task, participants were seated with their right leg positioned on a custom-made ankle

168 dynamometer. The knee was fully extended, the hip flexed at 70° (0° being fully extended),
169 and the ankle joint at 10° of plantar flexion (0° being the foot perpendicular to the shank). The
170 foot was secured with straps to a footplate connected to a load cell (SM-500 N, Interface,
171 Arizona, USA) to measure the isometric dorsiflexion force (**Figure 1B**). To ensure that the
172 force generated was exclusively due to the dorsiflexor muscles, additional straps were applied
173 around the thigh and knee. For the knee extension task, participants were seated on an isokinetic
174 dynamometer (Humac Norm Extremity System, CSMi Solutions, Massachusetts, USA) with
175 their right knee flexed at 90° (0° being fully extended) and aligned as coaxially as possible with
176 the dynamometer's axis of rotation (**Figure 1C**). The hip was flexed at 90° (0° being fully
177 extended), and the ankle joint was secured to the device approximately three centimeters above
178 the malleolus, allowing for the measurement of isometric knee extension force. The trunk and
179 waist were also secured to the device with Velcro straps.

180 The experimental procedures were the same for the three muscle groups (FDI, TA, and VM-
181 VL). Initially, participants performed three isometric maximal voluntary contractions (MVCs)
182 for 3 s, with 2 min of rest between each contraction. The highest MVC among the three trials
183 was used as a reference for the subsequent submaximal tasks. After a 5-min rest interval,
184 participants were asked to perform an isometric force-matching task, following a complex
185 trajectory for fifteen trials (learning task). This number of trials was chosen based on previous
186 studies, which have demonstrated that fifteen trials of a similar task are sufficient for short-
187 term learning (Knight and Kamen, 2004; Cabral et al., 2024b). The trajectory specifically
188 involved a linear increase from 0% MVC to the target force level at a rate of 5% MVC/s, a
189 stochastic force region at the target force level for 30 s, and a linear decrease from the target
190 force level to 0% MVC at a rate of -5% MVC/s (Cabral et al., 2024b). The stochastic force
191 region consisted of a randomly generated signal, low-pass filtered at 1.5 Hz, with oscillations
192 around the target force level, set at 5% MVC for the FDI muscle and 10% MVC for the TA

193 and VM-VL muscles. Three different trajectories were generated, one for each muscle group,
194 but the same trajectories were used for all trials and participants. A rest period of at least 1 min
195 was provided between trials. Throughout the task, participants were encouraged by the same
196 researcher to match the trajectory as closely as possible. Visual feedback from the target and
197 produced force was displayed on a computer monitor positioned approximately 60 cm in front
198 of the participant.

199

200

201 **Figure 1: Experimental setup.** Participants' positioning for the index finger abduction (A), dorsiflexion (B), and
202 knee extension (C) tasks. The isometric force produced by participants was measured using load cells (A, B) or
203 an isokinetic dynamometer (C). High-density surface electromyography grids with 64 electrodes were used to
204 record muscle activity from the first dorsal interosseous (A), tibialis anterior (B), and vastus medialis and vastus
205 lateralis (C). For all tasks, participants performed an isometric force-matching task following a complex
206 trajectory for 15 trials (learning task). The target force level was set at 5% of maximum voluntary contraction for
207 the first dorsal interosseous and 10% MVC for the tibialis anterior and vastii muscles.

208 **Data collection**

209 Monopolar high-density surface electromyograms (HDsEMG) were collected from the TA,
210 FDI, and VM-VL muscles during the submaximal isometric tasks using adhesive grids of 64
211 electrodes arranged into 13 rows by 5 columns, with a missing electrode in the upper left corner
212 (OT Bioelettronica, Turin, Italy). For the TA and VM-VL muscles, grids with an 8 mm inter-

213 electrode distance were used (GR08MM1305), while for the FDI muscle, grids with a 4 mm
214 inter-electrode distance (GR04MM1305) were employed. The grids were positioned
215 longitudinally along the muscle belly (**Figure 1**), which was identified through palpation by an
216 experienced investigator. In the case of the VL muscles, two grids were used: one positioned
217 distally and the other proximally. Before placing the electrodes, the skin was shaved and
218 cleaned with abrasive paste (EVERI, Spes Medica, Genova, Italy) and water to enhance signal
219 quality. Conductive paste (AC cream, Spes Medica, Genova, Italy) was applied in the foam
220 cavities of the grid to ensure optimal electrode-skin contact. The reference electrode was
221 positioned on the right ankle for TA and VM-VL muscles and on the right wrist for the FDI
222 muscle. HDsEMG and force signals were sampled synchronously at 2048 Hz using a 16-bit
223 A/D amplifier (10-500 Hz bandwidth; Quattrocento, OT Bioelettronica, Turin, Italy).

224 *Data analysis*

225 All analyses were conducted offline using custom-written scripts in MATLAB (version 2022b;
226 The MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, USA).

227 *Trial selection for analysis.* Three consecutive trials were selected out of the fifteen performed,
228 focusing on those after the learning of the force-matching skill (i.e., post-skill acquisition
229 trials). Initially, the force signal was low pass filtered at 15 Hz using a third-order Butterworth
230 filter. The root-mean-square error (RMSE) between the detrended force and target signals was
231 then calculated considering the 30-s middle region of each trial. The three consecutive trials
232 with the lowest RMSE between the force and target signals were selected for further analysis,
233 as the force oscillations are expected to be most similar across these trials. For these selected
234 trials, the coefficient of variation of force (i.e., standard deviation divided by mean) was
235 calculated to quantify force steadiness.

236 *HDsEMG decomposition and motor unit tracking.* Due to the late recruitment of motor units,
237 the first 5 seconds of data were discarded, and only the last 25 seconds of the middle region of
238 the three selected trials were analyzed. Initially, monopolar HDsEMG signals were filtered
239 between 20 and 500 Hz using a third-order bandpass Butterworth filter (**Figure 2A**). All signals
240 were then visually inspected, and those of low quality (e.g., artifacts or skin-electrode problems
241 during acquisition) were discarded from further analysis. The remaining HDsEMG signals
242 were decomposed into motor unit discharge times using a convolutive blind-source separation
243 algorithm (Negro et al., 2016b), which has been previously validated and widely applied to
244 assess individual motor units in the muscles investigated in this study (Negro et al., 2016b;
245 Martinez-Valdes et al., 2017; Cabral et al., 2024b). The identified motor units were visually
246 inspected by an experienced operator, and missing or misidentified discharges (inter-spike
247 intervals < 20 ms or > 250 ms; Negro et al. (2009)) were manually and iteratively edited
248 (Martinez-Valdes et al., 2017; Hug et al., 2021). Motor units were then tracked across the three
249 trials by reapplying the motor unit separation vectors, following procedures used in previous
250 studies (Oliveira and Negro, 2021; Rossato et al., 2022; Cabral et al., 2024b). Briefly, the
251 deconvolution of HDsEMG signals using independent component analysis involves the
252 calculation of a separation matrix, whose columns are the separation vectors for each motor
253 unit (Negro et al., 2016b; Dai and Hu, 2019). These separation vectors are unique for each
254 motor unit and define the spatiotemporal filters that, when applied to the HDsEMG signals,
255 yield the estimated motor unit discharge times. To maximize the number of tracked motor units,
256 the estimated separation vectors from one trial were applied in the other two trials, considering
257 all possible combinations. However, in a few cases (1 participant for TA, 3 for FDI and 2 for
258 the VM), it was not possible to track more than one unit using this method. In such cases, motor
259 units were tracked based on their action potential shapes (Martinez-Valdes et al., 2017).
260 Specifically, the two-dimensional representation of the motor unit action potentials identified

261 in one trial was estimated using the spike-triggered averaging technique and then cross-
 262 correlated with the spatial representation of the motor units identified in the other two trials.
 263 Motor units with high similarity between action potentials (cross-correlation > 0.8) were
 264 considered to belong to the same motor unit.
 265

266

267 **Figure 2: Linear dimensionality reduction analysis.** For the three post-skill acquisition trials selected for
 268 analysis, high-density surface electromyograms (HDsEMG) (A) were decomposed into motor unit discharge times
 269 using a convolutive blind source separation algorithm. The motor units were tracked across trials, and their
 270 discharge times were used to calculate binary motor unit spike trains (B). Low-pass filtered discharge rates of
 271 tracked motor units were obtained by convolving the motor unit spike trains with a 400-ms Hanning window (C).
 272 The standardized and detrended smoothed discharge rates were then used to estimate low-dimensional motor unit
 273 components via principal component analysis (PCA) and factor analysis (FA). Two components were extracted
 274 for all muscles analyzed (D).

275 Calculation of smoothed discharge rate matrices. The discharge times of the motor units
 276 tracked across the three post-skill acquisition trials were used to compute binary motor unit
 277 spike trains, where a value of 1 indicates the presence of a motor unit discharge at a specific
 278 time point, and a value of 0 indicates its absence (**Figure 2B**). The low-pass filtered discharge
 279 rates of motor units were then calculated by convolving the binary motor unit spike trains with
 280 a 400-ms Hanning window (Negro et al., 2009). To remove offsets and trends, these smoothed
 281 discharge rates were high-pass filtered at 0.75 Hz using a third-order Butterworth filter (De

282 Luca et al., 1982) and subsequently standardized to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1
283 (Jolliffe and Morgan (1992); **Figure 2C**). The resulting standardized and detrended smoothed
284 discharge rates, referred to as smoothed discharge rates for simplicity, were then arranged in a
285 $r \times c$ matrix, where r is the number of time samples and c is the number of motor units. This
286 matrix was used to estimate the neural components underlying the low-frequency oscillations
287 of motor units by applying linear dimensionality reduction techniques, specifically PCA and
288 FA. Additionally, a non-linear method (network-information framework) was employed to
289 characterize motor unit networks across trials.

290 Linear dimensionality reduction techniques. Two linear dimensionality reduction techniques,
291 PCA and FA, were used to extract the components underlying the smoothed discharge rates of
292 motor units (Jöreskog, 1967; Jolliffe and Morgan, 1992). An important step when applying PCA
293 or FA is to determine the number of low-dimensional components to retain. Various methods
294 have been proposed to determine this number, often based on the eigenvalues of each
295 component (Guttman, 1954; Kaiser, 1960; Horn, 1965; Cattell, 1966; Velicer, 1976). Given
296 previous evidence suggesting that parallel analysis is one of the most accurate methods for
297 identifying the ideal number of components, significantly outperforming other approaches
298 (Zwick and Velicer, 1986; Velicer et al., 2000; Hayton et al., 2004), we employed this method
299 to determine the number of motor unit components to extract. For a detailed tutorial on
300 performing parallel analysis, refer to Hayton et al. (2004). Briefly, we simulated a matrix of
301 random data by shuffling the time samples of the smoothed discharge rate matrices calculated
302 for each trial (see *Calculation of smoothed discharge rate matrices*). This random data matrix
303 was then subjected to PCA, and the estimated eigenvalues for each component were stored.
304 This procedure was repeated 1,000 times, resulting in a set of random eigenvalues from which
305 the average and 95% confidence intervals were calculated. The number of motor unit
306 components to retain was determined by identifying the eigenvalues extracted from the real

307 smoothed discharge rate matrices that exceeded the upper bound of the 95% confidence
308 interval of the random eigenvalues. This approach was performed separately for each of the
309 three selected trials, and the average across trials was calculated and retained for further
310 analysis.

311 Based on parallel analysis, which indicated extracting an average of one motor unit component
312 for individual muscles and two components for the VM-VL muscles (see *Results*), we extracted
313 two components for all analyses (**Figure 2D**). PCA and FA were applied without rotation to
314 motor units decomposed from individual muscles (TA, FDI, and VL) as well as synergistic
315 muscles (combined VM-VL). The VM muscle was not analyzed separately due to the low
316 number of motor units matched across trials (see *Results*). To investigate the association
317 between force oscillations and the two motor unit components, the cross-correlation between
318 the detrended signals was calculated (Negro et al., 2009). To assess the consistency of the two
319 motor unit components across trials, cross-correlation between trials was computed using 5-
320 second non-overlapping windows, with the resulting values averaged. Additionally, the
321 percentage of variance in the smoothed discharge rates explained by the two components
322 obtained through PCA was calculated and retained for analysis.

323 *Network-information framework.* To non-linearly characterize the connectivity between motor
324 unit smoothed discharge rates, we applied a framework combining information and network
325 theories (i.e., the network-information framework). The detailed methodology for this
326 approach has been described in previous studies (O'Reilly and Delis, 2022, 2024). First, the
327 non-linear relationships between smoothed discharge rates (**Figure 3A**) were estimated using
328 pairwise mutual information with a Gaussian copula-based approximation (Ince et al., 2017),
329 resulting in a symmetric adjacency matrix representing the connectivities between all motor
330 units (i.e., network-level functional connectivity; **Figure 3B**). A modified percolation analysis

331 (Gallos et al., 2012) was then applied to determine a threshold (the percolation threshold),
332 identifying only the significant associations between motor units (**Figure 3C**). Subsequently,
333 graph theory was employed to construct the motor unit network, where nodes (or vertices)
334 represent motor units, and edges (or links) denote significant associations between motor units
335 (**Figure 3D**). We used a circular representation to visually observe the matched motor units
336 across trials. As in the PCA and FA, this analysis was applied to motor units decomposed from
337 individual muscles (TA, FDI, and VL) as well as synergistic muscles (combined VM-VL).

338 To identify the neural components (or communities) within the motor unit network of each
339 post-skill acquisition trial, we applied a network community detection algorithm (Ahn et al.,
340 2010). This algorithm quantifies overlapping components through hierarchical clustering of
341 network links and outputs a binary matrix, where the rows represent the identified components,
342 and the columns represent the motor units in the network. A motor unit was assigned a value
343 of 1 if it belonged to a specific component and 0 otherwise. This process was performed
344 separately for each trial, and the average number of identified components across the three
345 trials was calculated. Two metrics were used to characterize the motor unit networks for each
346 post-skill acquisition trial. First, we calculated the network density, which quantifies the
347 number of edges in the network relative to the total possible number of edges. A higher network
348 density indicates stronger interconnections between nodes, reflecting a more cohesive network.
349 Additionally, we quantified the percentage of motor units belonging to the first component
350 (represented by green nodes in **Figure 3D**).

351

352 **Figure 3: Network-information analysis.** Pairwise mutual information, approximated using a Gaussian copula
 353 (Ince et al., 2017), was used to calculate non-linear relationships between smoothed discharge rates (A), resulting
 354 in a symmetric adjacency matrix (B). A modified percolation analysis (Gallos et al., 2012) identified significant
 355 associations between motor units (C). Graph theory was then applied to construct the motor unit network, where
 356 nodes (circles) represent motor units and edges (gray lines) denote significant associations (D). To identify neural
 357 components within the motor unit network, a network community detection algorithm was employed (Ahn et al.,
 358 2010), and the percentage of motor units belonging to the first component (green nodes in D) was quantified.

359 **Statistical analysis**

360 All statistical analyses were performed using R (version 4.3) within the RStudio environment
 361 (version 2023.06.0). To compare the RMSE between force and target, as well as the coefficient
 362 of variation of force across the three selected post-skill acquisition trials, Friedman tests were
 363 used with Bonferroni's post hoc correction for pairwise comparisons. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
 364 (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was applied to assess whether the smoothed discharge
 365 rate matrices were factorable (Kaiser, 1974). KMO values greater than 0.70 were considered
 366 indicative of matrices appropriate for factorization (Hoelzle and J. Meyer, 2012).

367 Linear mixed-effect models (LMMs) were used to compare the total variance explained in the
 368 smoothed discharge rates by the first and second motor unit components. Random intercept
 369 models were applied, with trial (trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3) and motor unit component (first and
 370 second motor unit components) as fixed effects, and participant as a random effect. To compare

371 the cross-correlation values between motor unit components and force, random intercept
372 models were also used, with trial (trial 1, trial 2, and trial 3), motor unit component (first and
373 second motor unit components) and linear method (PCA and FA) as fixed effects, and
374 participant as a random effect. Similarly, to compare the cross-correlation values of motor unit
375 components across trials, random intercept LMMs were used, with trial comparison (trial 1 vs.
376 trial 2, trial 1 vs. trial 3, and trial 2 vs. trial 3), motor unit component (first and second motor
377 unit components) and linear method (PCA and FA) as fixed effects, and participant as a random
378 effect. LMMs were implemented using the package *lmerTest* (Kuznetsova et al., 2017) with
379 the Kenward-Roger method to approximate the degrees of freedom and estimate the *p*-values.
380 The *emmeans* package was used for multiple comparisons and to calculate estimated marginal
381 means with 95% confidence intervals (Lenth et al., 2019).

382 To compare network density and the number of motor units belonging to the first component
383 across trials, Friedman tests were performed with Bonferroni's post hoc correction for pairwise
384 comparisons. All individual data of motor unit discharge times recorded for each muscle in the
385 three post-skill acquisition trials are available at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28324253>

386 **Results**

387 *Force oscillations across selected trials*

388 From the fifteen trials performed by each participant, we selected the three consecutive trials
389 following skill acquisition for analysis. **Figure 4A** provides a representative example of the
390 force oscillations observed in these trials. Visually, there is a clear overlap between the force
391 (colored traces) and target (gray traces) signals, along with a high degree of similarity in force
392 oscillations across trials. Consistent with these observations, no significant differences in force-
393 target RMSE were observed across trials for any of the tasks investigated (Friedman tests; $P >$
394 0.096 for all cases; **Figure 4B**). Similarly, no significant differences were observed in the
395 coefficient of variation of force across trials (Friedman tests; $P > 0.155$ for all cases). For the
396 TA, the average coefficient of variation of force values were $9.47 \pm 0.42\%$, $9.74 \pm 0.94\%$, and
397 $9.73 \pm 0.73\%$ for post-skill acquisition trials 1, 2, and 3, respectively. For the FDI, they were
398 $9.57 \pm 2.28\%$, $9.80 \pm 2.99\%$, and $9.30 \pm 2.36\%$ for post-skill acquisition trials 1, 2, and 3,
399 respectively. For the VM-VL, the values were $8.65 \pm 0.31\%$, $8.95 \pm 0.27\%$, and $9.14 \pm 0.61\%$
400 for post-skill acquisition trials 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

401

402 **Figure 4: Results of force oscillations across trials.** Comparison between force oscillations (colored lines) and
 403 the target (gray line) for the three consecutive post-skill acquisition trials selected for analysis (A). A high degree
 404 of similarity in force fluctuations across trials is evident. Group results of the root mean square error between
 405 the force and target are shown for the tibialis anterior (left panel in B), first dorsal interosseous (middle panel in
 406 B), and combined vastus medialis and vastus lateralis muscles (right panel in B). Circles represent individual
 407 participants. Horizontal lines, boxes, and whiskers denote the median value, interquartile range, and distribution
 408 range, respectively. VM, vastus medialis; VL, vastus lateralis.

409 **Characterization of low-dimensional motor unit control using PCA and FA**

410 To evaluate low-dimensional neural control underlying motor unit activity, we decomposed
 411 HDsEMG signals into individual motor unit spike trains and tracked the motor units across
 412 trials. The average number of matched motor units per participant was 16 ± 7 for the TA, $7 \pm$
 413 1 for the FDI, 3 ± 1 for the VM, and 12 ± 5 for the VL. All subsequent analysis were applied
 414 to matched motor units from individual muscles (TA, FDI, and VL) as well as synergistic
 415 muscles (combined VM-VL). We assessed whether the smoothed discharge rates of matched
 416 motor units were suitable for factor analysis. The KMO average values were 0.96 ± 0.03 for
 417 the TA, 0.90 ± 0.03 for the FDI, 0.87 ± 0.09 for the VL, and 0.91 ± 0.06 for the VM-VL,
 418 indicating that the smoothed discharge rate matrices for all muscles were appropriate for
 419 factorization.

420 Parallel analysis indicated that the average number of components to be extracted was $1.1 \pm$
421 0.3 for the TA motor units, 1.0 ± 0.2 for the FDI motor units, 1.6 ± 0.7 for the VL motor units,
422 and 2.0 ± 0.7 for the combined VM-VL motor units. We opted to extract two components for
423 all the muscles investigated using PCA and FA. For all muscles, the first motor unit component
424 explained significantly greater variance in the smoothed discharge rates compared with the
425 second motor unit component (LMMs; main effect of motor unit component; $P < 0.001$ for all
426 muscles). These differences were independent of the trial analyzed (LMMs; interaction effect
427 of motor unit component * trial; $P > 0.412$ for all muscles). The first motor unit component
428 accounted for an average variance of $80.7 \pm 6.6\%$ for the TA, $74.5 \pm 8.4\%$ for the FDI, $55.9 \pm$
429 9.9% for the VL, and $54.3 \pm 9.7\%$ for the VM-VL. The second component explained an average
430 variance of $4.8 \pm 2.2\%$ for the TA, $9.6 \pm 3.0\%$ for the FDI, $13.5 \pm 4.2\%$ for the VL, and $11.7 \pm$
431 3.6% for the VM-VL.

432 *Association between force oscillations and motor unit components*

433 To assess how effectively the neural components underlying motor unit activity explained force
434 oscillations, we calculated the cross-correlation between these signals. For all muscles, the first
435 motor unit component showed significantly greater cross-correlation values with force
436 compared to the second motor unit component (LMMs; main effect of motor unit component;
437 $P < 0.001$ for all muscles). These differences were independent of the trial analyzed and the
438 linear method used (LMMs; interaction effect of motor unit component * trial * linear method;
439 $P > 0.201$ for all muscles). Specifically, for the TA, the cross-correlation values with force
440 significantly increased from $0.07 [0.02, 0.13]$ for the second motor unit component to 0.52
441 $[0.46, 0.57]$ for the first motor unit component (**Figure 5A**). For the FDI, the values increased
442 from $0.22 [0.17, 0.27]$ to $0.56 [0.51, 0.61]$ between the second and first motor unit components
443 (**Figure 5B**). For the VL, the increases from the second to the first motor unit component were
444 from $0.06 [0.02, 0.11]$ to $0.50 [0.45, 0.54]$ (**Figure 5C**). For the VM-VL motor units, the cross-

445 correlation increased from 0.07 [0.02, 0.13] to 0.52 [0.46, 0.57] between the second and first
446 motor unit components (**Figure 5D**).

447

448 **Figure 5: Correlation between low-dimensional motor unit components and force.** To evaluate how effectively
449 the two low-dimensional motor unit components explained force oscillations, we calculated the cross-correlation
450 between these signals. Results are presented separately by method (principal component analysis and factor
451 analysis) and muscle: tibialis anterior (A), first dorsal interosseous (B), vastus lateralis (C), and combined vastus
452 lateralis and vastus medialis (D). Horizontal lines, boxes, and whiskers denote the median value, interquartile
453 range, and distribution range, respectively. * $p < 0.05$. VM, vastus medialis; VL, vastus lateralis.

454 **Consistency of motor unit components across trials**

455 **Figure 6** shows a representative case of the motor unit components extracted for each post-
456 skill acquisition trial using PCA. While the first motor unit component (**Figure 6A**) remained
457 highly consistent across trials, this similarity across trials was notably reduced for the second
458 motor unit component (**Figure 6B**). This was in line with the cross-correlation values
459 calculated between components, indicating an average of 0.78 ± 0.05 for the first component
460 and 0.36 ± 0.11 for the second component.

461

462 **Figure 6: Correlation of motor unit components across trials.** Representative example of the first (A) and second
 463 (B) motor unit components extracted during the three post-skill acquisition trials. Note the high similarity in
 464 oscillations of the first motor unit component across trials compared with the second component. Group results
 465 of the cross-correlation are shown for the tibialis anterior (A), first dorsal interosseous (B), vastus lateralis (C),
 466 and combined vastus lateralis and vastus medialis (D). Density curves compare the distribution of cross-
 467 correlation values for the first (purple) and second (green) motor unit components, with average values indicated.
 468 * $p < 0.05$. VM, vastus medialis; VL, vastus lateralis.

469 Consistent with the representative case, the group results revealed significantly greater cross-
 470 correlation values across trials for the first motor unit component compared to the second
 471 component (LMMs; main effect of motor unit component; $P < 0.001$ for all muscles),

472 regardless of the trial comparison and the linear method used (LMMs; interaction effect of
473 motor unit component * trial comparison * linear method; $P > 0.230$ for all muscles). For the
474 TA muscle, the cross-correlation values across trials significantly increased from 0.14 [0.07,
475 0.21] for the second motor unit component to 0.48 [0.41, 0.55] for the first motor unit
476 component (**Figure 6C**). For the FDI, these values increased from 0.11 [0.06, 0.16] to 0.52
477 [0.46, 0.57] between the second and first components (**Figure 6D**). In the VL, cross-correlation
478 across trials increased from 0.14 [0.03, 0.24] to 0.55 [0.45, 0.66] between the second and first
479 motor unit components (**Figure 6E**). Similarly, for the VM-VL motor units, the cross-
480 correlation increased from 0.18 [0.08, 0.29] to 0.58 [0.48, 0.69] between the second and first
481 components (**Figure 6F**).

482 *Characterization of motor unit networks across trials using network-information framework*

483 To assess the statistical dependence between pairs of motor unit smoothed discharge rates, we
484 characterized motor unit networks across consecutive trials using a network-information
485 framework. **Figure 7A** shows the significant pairwise mutual information between matched
486 motor units, along with the motor unit networks identified for the three consecutive trials. The
487 networks showed a high degree of similarity across trials, as evidenced by consistent
488 connections, such as those involving motor unit four (red edges) and motor unit sixteen (blue
489 edges). Additionally, the motor unit networks were generally denser (i.e., featuring a greater
490 number of connections), with most motor units belonging to the first motor unit component (or
491 community), as indicated by the green circles representing these motor units.

492

493 **Figure 7: Results of motor unit networks.** Representative example of non-linear pairwise mutual information
 494 analysis and the resulting motor unit networks for the three post-skill acquisition trials (A). Note the high
 495 similarity between motor unit networks, with most motor units belonging to the first component (green circles).
 496 The motor unit networks were characterized by high density (numerous connections). Group results are shown
 497 for network density (B) and the number of motor units belonging to the first component (C), separately by muscle
 498 and trial. Horizontal lines, boxes, and whiskers denote the median value, interquartile range, and distribution
 499 range, respectively. TA, tibialis anterior; FDI, first dorsal interosseous; VM, vastus medialis; VL, vastus lateralis.
 500

501 For the group results, the average number of identified motor unit components in the network
 502 was 1.6 ± 1.0 for the TA motor units, 1.0 ± 0.2 for the FDI motor units, 1.3 ± 0.7 for the VL
 503 motor units, and 1.4 ± 0.6 for the combined VM-VL motor units. No significant differences in
 504 network density were observed across trials for any of the muscles investigated (Friedman test;
 505 $P > 0.145$ for all cases; **Figure 7B**). Similarly, no significant differences were found across
 506 trials in the number of motor units belonging to the first motor unit component (Friedman test;
 507 $P > 0.345$ for all cases; **Figure 7C**), except for the FDI (Friedman test; $P = 0.047$). However,
 508 pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction did not reveal any significant differences
 509 between trials for the FDI ($P > 0.25$ for all pairwise comparisons).

510 **Discussion**

511 In this study, we investigated the relation between low-dimensional components underlying
512 motor unit discharge rates and oscillations in muscle force during repetitive isometric tasks
513 with highly similar force outputs. We first analyzed motor unit smoothed discharge rates of
514 individual (TA, FDI and VL) and synergistic (VM-VL) muscles using linear methods (PCA
515 and FA). Our results revealed that a single component was sufficient to explain most of the
516 variance in smoothed discharge rates. Notably, the first motor unit component showed
517 significantly greater correlations with force oscillations, compared to the second component,
518 and remained highly consistent across trials. These findings were further supported by a non-
519 linear method (network-information framework), which demonstrated high consistency in
520 motor unit networks across repetitive trials, as reflected by the high network density and the
521 inclusion of most motor units in the first motor unit component. As discussed below, these
522 outcomes collectively suggest that during isometric contractions, motor units are primarily
523 controlled by a single low-frequency synaptic input that closely resembles the output force
524 oscillations.

525 The concept of low-dimensional neural control has been extensively studied at the muscular
526 level, particularly through kinematics and surface EMG recordings, consistently demonstrating
527 that many movements can be explained by a small set of weighted combinations of muscle
528 activations (Lacquaniti et al., 2012; D'avella and Lacquaniti, 2013; Santello et al., 2013; Bruton
529 and O'Dwyer, 2018). Earlier observations of a high degree of correlation in the discharge rates
530 of individual motor units support the idea that low-dimensional control is not confined to the
531 muscular level but extends to the motor unit level (Datta & Stephens, 1990; De Luca et al.,
532 1982; Farmer et al., 1993; Kirkwood & Sears, 1978; Sears & Stagg, 1976). Common synaptic
533 inputs across motor neuron pools are believed to be the primary source of this correlated
534 activity and, consequently, the key determinant of alpha motor neuron control (Kirkwood and

535 Sears, 1978; De Luca et al., 1982; Datta et al., 1991; Conway et al., 1995; Baker et al., 1997;
536 Bräcklein et al., 2022a). While earlier evidence from this view came from correlation analysis
537 between motor unit pairs (De Luca et al., 1982; Datta et al., 1991; Conway et al., 1995),
538 subsequent simulation and experimental studies at the motor unit pool level demonstrated that
539 the effective neural drive to muscles is the common synaptic input to motor neurons (Negro et
540 al., 2009; Negro and Farina, 2011; Farina et al., 2014; Laine et al., 2015; Negro et al., 2016a;
541 Bräcklein et al., 2022b; Rossato et al., 2024). More recent studies using dimensionality
542 reduction methods have further corroborated the low-dimensional control of spinal motor
543 neurons, showing that one or two neural control signals are sufficient to explain motor unit
544 activity (Negro et al., 2009; Del Vecchio et al., 2023; Nuccio et al., 2024; Rossato et al., 2024).

545 Our findings align with this body of work, as we observed that a single component explained
546 most of the variance in motor unit discharge rates during isometric tasks using linear methods
547 (~70% across trials and muscles). In contrast, the second component explained substantially
548 less variance (~9% across trials and muscles), indicating that a single component was sufficient
549 to represent motor unit discharge patterns. These results were supported by the non-linear
550 framework, which demonstrated highly interconnected motor unit networks, with most units
551 belonging to the first motor unit component (**Figure 7**). The identification of a single dominant
552 component, through both linear and non-linear methods, suggests that the CNS employs a
553 simplified strategy for motor unit control, where common synaptic inputs play a crucial role in
554 force control. Interestingly, while a single component was retained for individual muscles,
555 parallel analysis indicated that an average of two components was needed for synergistic
556 control (combined VM-VL motor units). This finding aligns with other studies on the VM and
557 VL muscles that used different methods to determine the number of low-dimensional
558 components to retain (Del Vecchio et al., 2023; Nuccio et al., 2024; Rossato et al., 2024).
559 However, our results revealed that the second component accounted for only ~11% of VM-VL

560 motor unit activity, significantly less than the variance explained by the first component alone.
561 Additionally, as further discussed below, only the first motor unit component in VM-VL
562 largely explained oscillations in force (**Figure 5D**) and remained highly consistent across
563 repeated trials with similar motor outputs (**Figure 6F**). Moreover, when applying non-linear
564 methods, a single dominant component was identified on average in the motor unit networks,
565 even for the VM-VL motor units. These results suggest that the number of extracted
566 components for VM-VL motor units, particularly when using linear methods, does not
567 necessarily reflect the true dimensionality of motor unit control. This finding is consistent with
568 the recent study by Rossato et al. (2024), which showed that although two components were
569 extracted from VM-VL motor units, participants were unable to dissociate motor unit pair
570 activity during an online control paradigm. In agreement with this and prior work (Laine et al.,
571 2015), our results support the presence of a dominant common input driving force control in
572 the VM and VL muscles.

573 Mathematically, muscle force can be modeled as the convolution of the neural drive to the
574 muscle (i.e., the cumulative motor unit spike train) with the average twitch of active motor
575 units (Dideriksen et al., 2012; Negro and Orizio, 2017). Because twitch contractile properties
576 act as a low-pass filter on the neural drive (Bawa and Stein, 1976; Baldissera et al., 1998;
577 Cabral et al., 2024a), only the low-frequency oscillations in the neural drive are effectively
578 transmitted to the force. Consequently, force oscillations are primarily determined by the low-
579 frequency components of the common synaptic inputs to spinal motor neurons (for a review,
580 see Farina and Negro (2015)). From a motor unit population perspective, these low-frequency
581 components of shared inputs can be estimated from low-pass filtered motor unit discharge rates
582 (e.g., using a Hanning window), either via dimensionality reduction techniques (Negro et al.,
583 2009; Del Vecchio et al., 2023) or coherence analysis between motor unit spike trains (Negro
584 and Farina, 2012; Castronovo et al., 2015; Cabral et al., 2024b; Cabral et al., 2024a). Given

585 that dimensionality reduction methods, as applied in the current study, provide time-varying
586 signals, their fluctuations are expected to closely resemble force oscillations if they are indeed
587 determinants of force control. Our results corroborate this hypothesis, particularly the
588 observation that the first motor unit component was correlated with force oscillations by ~55%
589 across all investigated muscles (**Figure 5**). This correlation was consistent across trials and
590 independent of the linear method used. Notably, only the first component closely resembled
591 force oscillations, whereas the second component showed an average correlation of just ~12%
592 across muscles. These findings, consistent with previous work (Negro et al., 2009), strongly
593 suggest that a single dominant common input is the primary determinant of force control and
594 modulation, at least for the muscles investigated in this study.

595 An important consideration is that, despite the strong correlation between the first component
596 and force oscillations, the correlation values did not approach 1 (i.e., perfect correlation).
597 Several factors could explain this discrepancy. First, motor unit discharge rates are influenced
598 by common noise inputs, which introduce variability into the neural drive signal and affect
599 force modulation (Harris and Wolpert, 1998; Cabral et al., 2024b). Second, the muscle-tendon
600 system introduces non-linearities that affect the translation of motor unit activity into force
601 output (Perreault et al., 2003; Lubel et al., 2023). Third, variability in the shape of motor unit
602 twitches may contribute to differences between predicted and actual force oscillations. In this
603 study, smoothed discharge rates were obtained by convolving motor unit spike trains with the
604 same Hanning window for all motor units. Previous studies have shown that using a window
605 shape more closely resembling motor unit twitch force can yield higher correlations between
606 the first low-dimensional motor unit component and force fluctuations (Negro et al., 2009).
607 Finally, while linear methods effectively capture the patterns of shared synaptic inputs (Negro
608 and Farina, 2011, 2012), they may not fully account for the non-linear dynamics inherent in
609 force production. Non-linear methods, such as those employed in this study (O'Reilly and

610 Delis, 2022, 2024), can provide complementary insights by modeling the complex interactions
611 within motor unit networks. For instance, the network-information framework revealed highly
612 interconnected motor unit networks, emphasizing the role of shared inputs in driving force
613 production (**Figure 7B**). Furthermore, most of the units belonged to the first motor unit
614 component (~80% across trials and muscles), and this pattern remained consistent across trials
615 (**Figure 7C**). By capturing these higher-order interactions, non-linear methods can address
616 limitations of linear approaches, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the neural
617 control of force. The framework used in this study, along with high-order correlation methods
618 (O'Reilly and Delis, 2024; O'Reilly et al., 2025), could be further explored in future research
619 to provide better insights into motor unit control.

620 Another important finding of this study is the high consistency of the first component across
621 trials, with average correlation values of approximately 0.6 across all investigated muscles
622 (**Figure 6**). This suggests that low-dimensional control is not only effective in reducing the
623 complexity of motor unit control but also provides a reliable and repeatable mechanism for
624 force modulation. The high trial-to-trial consistency of the first component, but not the second,
625 reinforces the idea that a single dominant control input driving motor unit activity is a
626 purposeful strategy employed by the CNS to simplify coordination, particularly during
627 repetitive tasks with similar motor outputs. There is an ongoing debate about whether low-
628 dimensional control reflects a neural control scheme (i.e., hard-wired) or emerges as a
629 consequence of task constraints (i.e., soft-assembled) (Tresch and Jarc, 2009; Kutch and
630 Valero-Cuevas, 2012). While our experimental approach does not allow definitive conclusions
631 regarding this question, we observed that the production and modulation of force after a new
632 skill acquisition task was achieved through a single dominant control input that remained
633 consistent across repeated trials of the same task.

634 *Methodological considerations*

635 In this section, we would like to discuss several methodological considerations. Based on the
636 number of trials of previous experiments involving short-term learning tasks (Knight and
637 Kamen, 2004; Cabral et al., 2024b), our protocol was designed to ensure consistent motor
638 outputs across trials, which was essential for analyzing the stability of motor unit low-
639 dimensional components. Our results indicated that performing 15 trials of the proposed task
640 was sufficient to obtain a sequence of three post-skill acquisition trials with highly similar
641 motor outputs (**Figure 4**). This was further confirmed by the absence of significant changes in
642 force steadiness (i.e., coefficient of variation of force) between selected trials. Compared to
643 previous studies that examining low-dimensional control of motor unit activity (Negro et al.,
644 2009; Del Vecchio et al., 2023; Nuccio et al., 2024), our protocol provided a distinct advantage
645 by facilitating the evaluation of the consistency of neural control strategies.

646 Another important methodological point concerns the determination of the number of low-
647 dimensional components to retain (Patil et al., 2008; Izquierdo et al., 2014; Iacobucci et al.,
648 2022). Various methods have been proposed in the literature, including the ‘eigenvalue ≥ 1 ’
649 criterion (Guttman, 1954; Kaiser, 1960), the scree plot test (Cattell, 1966), the minimum
650 average partials criterion (Velicer, 1976), and parallel analysis (Horn, 1965). Parallel analysis,
651 which compares observed eigenvalues with those generated from random data, has been shown
652 to outperform other approaches for selecting the number of components (Zwick and Velicer,
653 1986; Velicer et al., 2000; Hayton et al., 2004). To our knowledge, this is the first study to
654 apply parallel analysis for selecting low-dimensional motor unit components. Given its
655 consistency in determining the number of components across trials and muscles, as well as its
656 data-driven nature, we recommend this approach for future studies exploring low-dimensional
657 motor unit control.

658 The choice of dimensionality reduction method is another critical consideration that can affect
659 the interpretation of results (Tresch et al., 2006; Cunningham and Yu, 2014; Bruton and
660 O'Dwyer, 2018). While PCA and FA are often used interchangeably, they differ in theoretical
661 and mathematical assumptions (Hoelzle and J. Meyer, 2012). PCA calculates linear
662 combinations of measured variables (i.e., components) that maximize explained variance,
663 including both common and unique variances. FA, on the other hand, separates common
664 variance from unique variance, identifying latent constructs that explain shared variance among
665 variables. Conceptually, PCA and FA differ in their approach directionality: PCA models how
666 measured variables influence components, whereas FA assumes that latent factors drive the
667 measured variables. For estimating commonality in motor unit discharge patterns, FA is
668 advantageous because it focuses exclusively on shared variance across variables. However,
669 PCA is mathematically linked to Hebbian theory (Oja, 1989, 1992; Olshausen, 1998),
670 providing a solid foundation for its use in analyzing patterns of covariation within neuronal
671 ensembles (Chapin and Nicolelis, 1999; Negro et al., 2009; Churchland et al., 2010; Levine et
672 al., 2023). In this study, the choice of linear method (PCA or FA) did not affect the results for
673 any of the investigated muscles, as we focused on correlations between motor unit components
674 and force fluctuations, as well as consistency across similar trials. Future research should select
675 dimensionality reduction methods a priori, based on the specific research question and
676 underlying assumptions.

677 We chose not to apply component rotations in this study, as done in recent research (Del
678 Vecchio et al., 2023; Nuccio et al., 2024), and would like to briefly address this decision. PCA
679 assumes that extracted components are orthogonal, whereas FA can incorporate orthogonal
680 (e.g., varimax) or oblique (e.g., promax) rotations to the initial factor solution. It is important
681 to note that rotation redistributes variance across components, reducing the total variance
682 explained by individual components due to changes in the partitioning of variance (Abdi,

683 2003). Consequently, rotating the components affects the correlations between individual
684 motor unit discharge rates and components (i.e., loadings). For instance, oblique rotations such
685 as promax may increase the correlation of certain original variables with one component while
686 reducing it with another, thereby facilitating interpretation in specific applications where such
687 associations may be expected (e.g., social sciences). In this study, we assumed uncorrelated
688 components (i.e., orthogonal) for simplicity and conceptual clearness of the interpretation. In
689 fact, if components are correlated, they may, in theory, be better interpreted as generated by a
690 single synaptic input. Since component rotation is applied primarily to facilitate interpretation,
691 future studies should investigate the physiological implications of perpendicular or oblique
692 components.

693 Lastly, the non-linear analysis combining information theory and network-based approaches
694 has provided novel insights into motor unit behavior. This framework has been recently applied
695 to surface electromyograms to characterize neuromuscular networks (O'Reilly and Delis, 2024;
696 O'Reilly et al., 2025). In this study, we extended this approach to motor unit discharge rates
697 and demonstrated its potential to reveal important features of low-dimensional motor unit
698 control during isometric contractions. By capturing complex interactions beyond traditional
699 linear methods, this framework offers a promising tool for future research investigating motor
700 unit network structure and its role in neural control strategies.

701 ***Conclusions***

702 In conclusion, our results provide strong evidence for low-dimensional neural control at the
703 motor unit level, where a single dominant component is sufficient to explain the majority of
704 motor unit discharge activity and force oscillations. The high consistency of this component
705 across trials further supports the idea that low-dimensional control is a reliable and efficient
706 strategy employed by the CNS for repetitive isometric tasks. Future studies should investigate

707 the generalizability of these findings to other muscles and motor tasks with greater degrees of
708 freedom. Lastly, we offer methodological recommendations to enhance the use and
709 replicability of linear dimensionality reduction methods in motor unit research.

710 **References**

- 711 Abdi H (2003) Factor rotations in factor analyses. In: Encyclopedia for Research Methods for
712 the Social Sciences (Lewis-Beck M, Bryman A, Futing T, eds). Thousand Oaks (CA):
713 Sage.
- 714 Ahn Y-Y, Bagrow JP, Lehmann S (2010) Link communities reveal multiscale complexity in
715 networks. *Nature* 466:761-764.
- 716 Alessandro C, Delis I, Nori F, Panzeri S, Berret B (2013) Muscle synergies in neuroscience
717 and robotics: from input-space to task-space perspectives. *Frontiers in Computational*
718 *Neuroscience* 7.
- 719 Baker SN, Olivier E, Lemon RN (1997) Coherent oscillations in monkey motor cortex and
720 hand muscle EMG show task-dependent modulation. *J Physiol* 501 (Pt 1):225-241.
- 721 Baldissera F, Cavallari P, Cerri G (1998) Motoneuronal pre-compensation for the low-pass
722 filter characteristics of muscle. A quantitative appraisal in cat muscle units. *J Physiol*
723 511 (Pt 2):611-627.
- 724 Bawa P, Stein RB (1976) Frequency response of human soleus muscle. *J Neurophysiol* 39:788-
725 793.
- 726 Bernshtein NA (1967) *The Co-ordination and Regulation of Movements*: Pergamon Press.
- 727 Bizzi E, Cheung VC, d'Avella A, Saltiel P, Tresch M (2008) Combining modules for
728 movement. *Brain Res Rev* 57:125-133.
- 729 Bräcklein M, Barsakcioglu DY, Del Vecchio A, Ibáñez J, Farina D (2022a) Reading and
730 Modulating Cortical β Bursts from Motor Unit Spiking Activity. *J Neurosci* 42:3611-
731 3621.
- 732 Bräcklein M, Barsakcioglu DY, Ibáñez J, Eden J, Burdet E, Mehring C, Farina D (2022b) The
733 control and training of single motor units in isometric tasks are constrained by a
734 common input signal. *eLife* 11:e72871.
- 735 Bruton M, O'Dwyer N (2018) Synergies in coordination: a comprehensive overview of neural,
736 computational, and behavioral approaches. *J Neurophysiol* 120:2761-2774.
- 737 Cabral HV, Inglis JG, Cudicio A, Cogliati M, Orizio C, Yavuz US, Negro F (2024a) Muscle
738 contractile properties directly influence shared synaptic inputs to spinal motor neurons.
739 *The Journal of Physiology* 602:2855-2872.
- 740 Cabral HV, Cudicio A, Bonardi A, Del Vecchio A, Falciati L, Orizio C, Martinez-Valdes E,
741 Negro F (2024b) Neural Filtering of Physiological Tremor Oscillations to Spinal Motor
742 Neurons Mediates Short-Term Acquisition of a Skill Learning Task. *eneuro*
743 11:ENEURO.0043-0024.2024.
- 744 Castronovo AM, Negro F, Conforto S, Farina D (2015) The proportion of common synaptic
745 input to motor neurons increases with an increase in net excitatory input. *J Appl Physiol*
746 (1985) 119:1337-1346.

- 747 Cattell RB (1966) The Scree Test For The Number Of Factors. *Multivariate Behav Res* 1:245-
748 276.
- 749 Chapin JK, Nicolelis MA (1999) Principal component analysis of neuronal ensemble activity
750 reveals multidimensional somatosensory representations. *J Neurosci Methods* 94:121-
751 140.
- 752 Chen M, Zhou P (2016) A Novel Framework Based on FastICA for High Density Surface
753 EMG Decomposition. *IEEE Trans Neural Syst Rehabil Eng* 24:117-127.
- 754 Churchland MM, Cunningham JP, Kaufman MT, Ryu SI, Shenoy KV (2010) Cortical
755 Preparatory Activity: Representation of Movement or First Cog in a Dynamical
756 Machine? *Neuron* 68:387-400.
- 757 Conway BA, Halliday DM, Farmer SF, Shahani U, Maas P, Weir AI, Rosenberg JR (1995)
758 Synchronization between motor cortex and spinal motoneuronal pool during the
759 performance of a maintained motor task in man. *J Physiol* 489 (Pt 3):917-924.
- 760 Cunningham JP, Yu BM (2014) Dimensionality reduction for large-scale neural recordings.
761 *Nature Neuroscience* 17:1500-1509.
- 762 D'avella A, Lacquaniti F (2013) Control of reaching movements by muscle synergy
763 combinations. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience* 7.
- 764 d'Avella A, Saltiel P, Bizzi E (2003) Combinations of muscle synergies in the construction of
765 a natural motor behavior. *Nature Neuroscience* 6:300-308.
- 766 d'Avella A, Portone A, Lacquaniti F (2011) Superposition and modulation of muscle synergies
767 for reaching in response to a change in target location. *Journal of Neurophysiology*
768 106:2796-2812.
- 769 Dai C, Hu X (2019) Independent component analysis based algorithms for high-density
770 electromyogram decomposition: Systematic evaluation through simulation. *Computers*
771 *in Biology and Medicine* 109:171-181.
- 772 Datta AK, Farmer SF, Stephens JA (1991) Central nervous pathways underlying
773 synchronization of human motor unit firing studied during voluntary contractions. *J*
774 *Physiol* 432:401-425.
- 775 De Luca CJ, LeFever RS, McCue MP, Xenakis AP (1982) Control scheme governing
776 concurrently active human motor units during voluntary contractions. *J Physiol*
777 329:129-142.
- 778 De N RL (1938) ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITY OF THE CHAINS OF INTERNUNCIAL
779 NEURONS. *Journal of Neurophysiology* 1:207-244.
- 780 Del Vecchio A, Marconi Germer C, Kinf TM, Nuccio S, Hug F, Eskofier B, Farina D, Enoka
781 RM (2023) The Forces Generated by Agonist Muscles during Isometric Contractions
782 Arise from Motor Unit Synergies. *J Neurosci* 43:2860-2873.

- 783 Dideriksen JL, Negro F, Enoka RM, Farina D (2012) Motor unit recruitment strategies and
784 muscle properties determine the influence of synaptic noise on force steadiness. *Journal*
785 *of Neurophysiology* 107:3357-3369.
- 786 Ebitz RB, Hayden BY (2021) The population doctrine in cognitive neuroscience. *Neuron*
787 109:3055-3068.
- 788 Farina D, Negro F (2015) Common synaptic input to motor neurons, motor unit
789 synchronization, and force control. *Exerc Sport Sci Rev* 43:23-33.
- 790 Farina D, Negro F, Dideriksen JL (2014) The effective neural drive to muscles is the common
791 synaptic input to motor neurons. *J Physiol* 592:3427-3441.
- 792 Farmer SF, Bremner FD, Halliday DM, Rosenberg JR, Stephens JA (1993) The frequency
793 content of common synaptic inputs to motoneurons studied during voluntary isometric
794 contraction in man. *J Physiol* 470:127-155.
- 795 Gallego JA, Perich MG, Miller LE, Solla SA (2017) Neural Manifolds for the Control of
796 Movement. *Neuron* 94:978-984.
- 797 Gallos LK, Makse HA, Sigman M (2012) A small world of weak ties provides optimal global
798 integration of self-similar modules in functional brain networks. *Proceedings of the*
799 *National Academy of Sciences* 109:2825-2830.
- 800 Gao P, Ganguli S (2015) On simplicity and complexity in the brave new world of large-scale
801 neuroscience. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology* 32:148-155.
- 802 Gentner R, Classen J (2006) Modular Organization of Finger Movements by the Human
803 Central Nervous System. *Neuron* 52:731-742.
- 804 Georgopoulos AP, Kalaska JF, Caminiti R, Massey JT (1982) On the relations between the
805 direction of two-dimensional arm movements and cell discharge in primate motor
806 cortex. *J Neurosci* 2:1527-1537.
- 807 Giszter S, Patil V, Hart C (2007) Primitives, premotor drives, and pattern generation: a
808 combined computational and neuroethological perspective. In: *Progress in Brain*
809 *Research* (Cisek P, Drew T, Kalaska JF, eds), pp 323-346: Elsevier.
- 810 Guttman L (1954) Some necessary conditions for common-factor analysis. *Psychometrika*
811 19:149-161.
- 812 Harris CM, Wolpert DM (1998) Signal-dependent noise determines motor planning. *Nature*
813 394:780-784.
- 814 Hatsopoulos NG, Ojakangas CL, Paninski L, Donoghue JP (1998) Information about
815 movement direction obtained from synchronous activity of motor cortical neurons.
816 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 95:15706-15711.
- 817 Hayton JC, Allen DG, Scarpello V (2004) Factor Retention Decisions in Exploratory Factor
818 Analysis: a Tutorial on Parallel Analysis. *Organizational Research Methods* 7:191-205.

- 819 Hebb DO (1949) *The organization of behavior; a neuropsychological theory*. Oxford, England:
820 Wiley.
- 821 Hoelzle JB, J. Meyer G (2012) *Exploratory Factor Analysis: Basics and Beyond*. In: *Handbook*
822 *of Psychology, Second Edition*.
- 823 Holobar A, Zazula D (2007) Multichannel Blind Source Separation Using Convolution Kernel
824 Compensation. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* 55:4487-4496.
- 825 Horn JL (1965) A RATIONALE AND TEST FOR THE NUMBER OF FACTORS IN
826 FACTOR ANALYSIS. *Psychometrika* 30:179-185.
- 827 Hug F, Avrillon S, Sarcher A, Del Vecchio A, Farina D (2023) Correlation networks of spinal
828 motor neurons that innervate lower limb muscles during a multi-joint isometric task. *J*
829 *Physiol* 601:3201-3219.
- 830 Hug F, Avrillon S, Del Vecchio A, Casolo A, Ibanez J, Nuccio S, Rossato J, Holobar A, Farina
831 D (2021) Analysis of motor unit spike trains estimated from high-density surface
832 electromyography is highly reliable across operators. *J Electromyogr Kinesiol*
833 58:102548.
- 834 Iacobucci D, Ruvio A, Román S, Moon S, Herr PM (2022) How many factors in factor
835 analysis? New insights about parallel analysis with confidence intervals. *Journal of*
836 *Business Research* 139:1026-1043.
- 837 Ince RA, Giordano BL, Kayser C, Rousselet GA, Gross J, Schyns PG (2017) A statistical
838 framework for neuroimaging data analysis based on mutual information estimated via
839 a gaussian copula. *Hum Brain Mapp* 38:1541-1573.
- 840 Ivanenko YP, Cappellini G, Dominici N, Poppele RE, Lacquaniti F (2005) Coordination of
841 Locomotion with Voluntary Movements in Humans. *The Journal of Neuroscience*
842 25:7238-7253.
- 843 Izquierdo I, Olea J, Abad FJ (2014) Exploratory factor analysis in validation studies: uses and
844 recommendations. *Psicothema* 26:395-400.
- 845 Joliffe I, Morgan B (1992) Principal component analysis and exploratory factor analysis.
846 *Statistical Methods in Medical Research* 1:69-95.
- 847 Jöreskog KG (1967) Some contributions to maximum likelihood factor analysis.
848 *Psychometrika* 32:443-482.
- 849 Kaiser HF (1960) The Application of Electronic Computers to Factor Analysis. *Educational*
850 *and Psychological Measurement* 20:141-151.
- 851 Kaiser HF (1974) An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika* 39:31-36.
- 852 Kipke DR, Shain W, Buzsáki G, Fetz E, Henderson JM, Hetke JF, Schalk G (2008) Advanced
853 neurotechnologies for chronic neural interfaces: new horizons and clinical
854 opportunities. *J Neurosci* 28:11830-11838.

- 855 Kirkwood PA, Sears TA (1978) The synaptic connexions to intercostal motoneurons as
856 revealed by the average common excitation potential. *J Physiol* 275:103-134.
- 857 Knight CA, Kamen G (2004) Enhanced motor unit rate coding with improvements in a force-
858 matching task. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology* 14:619-629.
- 859 Kutch JJ, Valero-Cuevas FJ (2012) Challenges and new approaches to proving the existence
860 of muscle synergies of neural origin. *PLoS Comput Biol* 8:e1002434.
- 861 Kuznetsova A, Brockhoff PB, Christensen RHB (2017) lmerTest Package: Tests in Linear
862 Mixed Effects Models. *Journal of Statistical Software* 82:1 - 26.
- 863 Lacquaniti F, Ivanenko YP, Zago M (2012) Patterned control of human locomotion. *The*
864 *Journal of Physiology* 590:2189-2199.
- 865 Laine CM, Martinez-Valdes E, Falla D, Mayer F, Farina D (2015) Motor Neuron Pools of
866 Synergistic Thigh Muscles Share Most of Their Synaptic Input. *J Neurosci* 35:12207-
867 12216.
- 868 Latash ML, Scholz JP, Schöner G (2007) Toward a new theory of motor synergies. *Motor*
869 *Control* 11:276-308.
- 870 Lenth R, Singmann H, Love J, Buerkner P, Herve M (2019) Package ‘emmeans’. In.
- 871 Levine J, Avrillon S, Farina D, Hug F, Pons JL (2023) Two motor neuron synergies, invariant
872 across ankle joint angles, activate the triceps surae during plantarflexion. *The Journal*
873 *of Physiology* 601:4337-4354.
- 874 Liddell EGT, Sherrington CS (1925) Recruitment and some other features of reflex inhibition.
875 *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London Series B, Containing Papers of a*
876 *Biological Character* 97:488-518.
- 877 Lubel E, Sgambato BG, Rohlen R, Ibanez J, Barsakcioglu DY, Tang MX, Farina D (2023)
878 Non-Linearity in Motor Unit Velocity Twitch Dynamics: Implications for Ultrafast
879 Ultrasound Source Separation. *IEEE Trans Neural Syst Rehabil Eng* 31:3699-3710.
- 880 Madarshahian S, Letizi J, Latash ML (2021) Synergic control of a single muscle: The example
881 of flexor digitorum superficialis. *J Physiol* 599:1261-1279.
- 882 Martinez-Valdes E, Negro F, Laine CM, Falla D, Mayer F, Farina D (2017) Tracking motor
883 units longitudinally across experimental sessions with high-density surface
884 electromyography. *J Physiol* 595:1479-1496.
- 885 Muceli S, Poppendieck W, Holobar A, Gandevia S, Liebetanz D, Farina D (2022) Blind
886 identification of the spinal cord output in humans with high-density electrode arrays
887 implanted in muscles. *Science Advances* 8:eabo5040.
- 888 Muceli S, Poppendieck W, Negro F, Yoshida K, Hoffmann KP, Butler JE, Gandevia SC, Farina
889 D (2015) Accurate and representative decoding of the neural drive to muscles in
890 humans with multi-channel intramuscular thin-film electrodes. *J Physiol* 593:3789-
891 3804.

- 892 Negro F, Farina D (2011) Linear transmission of cortical oscillations to the neural drive to
893 muscles is mediated by common projections to populations of motoneurons in humans.
894 *J Physiol* 589:629-637.
- 895 Negro F, Farina D (2012) Factors influencing the estimates of correlation between motor unit
896 activities in humans. *PLoS One* 7:e44894.
- 897 Negro F, Orizio C (2017) Robust estimation of average twitch contraction forces of populations
898 of motor units in humans. *J Electromyogr Kinesiol* 37:132-140.
- 899 Negro F, Holobar A, Farina D (2009) Fluctuations in isometric muscle force can be described
900 by one linear projection of low-frequency components of motor unit discharge rates. *J*
901 *Physiol* 587:5925-5938.
- 902 Negro F, Yavuz U, Farina D (2016a) The human motor neuron pools receive a dominant slow-
903 varying common synaptic input. *J Physiol* 594:5491-5505.
- 904 Negro F, Muceli S, Castronovo AM, Holobar A, Farina D (2016b) Multi-channel intramuscular
905 and surface EMG decomposition by convolutive blind source separation. *J Neural Eng*
906 13:026027.
- 907 Nuccio S, Germer CM, Casolo A, Borzuola R, Labanca L, Rocchi JE, Mariani PP, Felici F,
908 Farina D, Falla D, Macaluso A, Sbriccoli P, Del Vecchio A (2024) Neuroplastic
909 alterations in common synaptic inputs and synergistic motor unit clusters controlling
910 the vastii muscles of individuals with ACL reconstruction. *J Appl Physiol* (1985)
911 137:835-847.
- 912 O'Reilly D, Delis I (2022) A network information theoretic framework to characterise muscle
913 synergies in space and time. *J Neural Eng* 19:016031.
- 914 O'Reilly D, Delis I (2024) Dissecting muscle synergies in the task space. *eLife* 12:RP87651.
- 915 O'Reilly D, Shaw W, Hilt P, de Castro Aguiar R, Astill SL, Delis I (2025) Quantifying the
916 diverse contributions of hierarchical muscle interactions to motor function. *iScience*
917 28:111613.
- 918 Oja E (1989) Neural networks, principal components, and subspaces. *International journal of*
919 *neural systems* 1:61-68.
- 920 Oja E (1992) Principal components, minor components, and linear neural networks. *Neural*
921 *Networks* 5:927-935.
- 922 Oliveira AS, Negro F (2021) Neural control of matched motor units during muscle shortening
923 and lengthening at increasing velocities. *J Appl Physiol* (1985) 130:1798-1813.
- 924 Olshausen BA (1998) Linear Hebbian learning and PCA.
- 925 Overduin SA, d'Avella A, Roh J, Bizzi E (2008) Modulation of Muscle Synergy Recruitment
926 in Primate Grasping. *The Journal of Neuroscience* 28:880-892.

- 927 Patil VH, Singh SN, Mishra S, Todd Donovan D (2008) Efficient theory development and
928 factor retention criteria: Abandon the ‘eigenvalue greater than one’ criterion. *Journal*
929 *of Business Research* 61:162-170.
- 930 Perreault EJ, Day SJ, Hulliger M, Heckman CJ, Sandercock TG (2003) Summation of Forces
931 From Multiple Motor Units in the Cat Soleus Muscle. *Journal of Neurophysiology*
932 89:738-744.
- 933 Rossato J, Avrillon S, Tucker K, Farina D, Hug F (2024) The volitional control of individual
934 motor units is constrained within low-dimensional neural manifolds by common inputs.
935 *The Journal of Neuroscience*:e0702242024.
- 936 Rossato J, Tucker K, Avrillon S, Lacourpaille L, Holobar A, Hug F (2022) Less common
937 synaptic input between muscles from the same group allows for more flexible
938 coordination strategies during a fatiguing task. *J Neurophysiol* 127:421-433.
- 939 Saltiel P, Wyler-Duda K, D'Avella A, Tresch MC, Bizzi E (2001) Muscle synergies encoded
940 within the spinal cord: evidence from focal intraspinal NMDA iontophoresis in the frog.
941 *J Neurophysiol* 85:605-619.
- 942 Santello M, Baud-Bovy G, Jörntell H (2013) Neural bases of hand synergies. *Frontiers in*
943 *Computational Neuroscience* 7.
- 944 Saxena S, Cunningham JP (2019) Towards the neural population doctrine. *Current Opinion in*
945 *Neurobiology* 55:103-111.
- 946 Sherrington CS (1925) Remarks on some aspects of reflex inhibition. *Proceedings of the Royal*
947 *Society of London Series B, Containing Papers of a Biological Character* 97:519-545.
- 948 Soechting JF, Lacquaniti F (1989) An assessment of the existence of muscle synergies during
949 load perturbations and intentional movements of the human arm. *Exp Brain Res*
950 74:535-548.
- 951 Steinmetz NA et al. (2021) Neuropixels 2.0: A miniaturized high-density probe for stable, long-
952 term brain recordings. *Science* 372:eabf4588.
- 953 Thompson CK, Negro F, Johnson MD, Holmes MR, McPherson LM, Powers RK, Farina D,
954 Heckman CJ (2018) Robust and accurate decoding of motoneuron behaviour and
955 prediction of the resulting force output. *J Physiol* 596:2643-2659.
- 956 Ting LH, Macpherson JM (2005) A limited set of muscle synergies for force control during a
957 postural task. *J Neurophysiol* 93:609-613.
- 958 Ting LH, Chiel HJ, Trumbower RD, Allen JL, McKay JL, Hackney ME, Kesar TM (2015)
959 Neuromechanical principles underlying movement modularity and their implications
960 for rehabilitation. *Neuron* 86:38-54.
- 961 Tresch MC, Jarc A (2009) The case for and against muscle synergies. *Curr Opin Neurobiol*
962 19:601-607.
- 963 Tresch MC, Saltiel P, Bizzi E (1999) The construction of movement by the spinal cord. *Nature*
964 *Neuroscience* 2:162-167.

- 965 Tresch MC, Cheung VCK, d'Avella A (2006) Matrix Factorization Algorithms for the
966 Identification of Muscle Synergies: Evaluation on Simulated and Experimental Data
967 Sets. *Journal of Neurophysiology* 95:2199-2212.
- 968 Tresch MC, Saltiel P, d'Avella A, Bizzi E (2002) Coordination and localization in spinal motor
969 systems. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev* 40:66-79.
- 970 Velicer WF (1976) Determining the number of components from the matrix of partial
971 correlations. *Psychometrika* 41:321-327.
- 972 Velicer WF, Eaton CA, Fava JL (2000) Construct Explication through Factor or Component
973 Analysis: A Review and Evaluation of Alternative Procedures for Determining the
974 Number of Factors or Components. In: *Problems and Solutions in Human Assessment:
975 Honoring Douglas N. Jackson at Seventy* (Goffin RD, Helmes E, eds), pp 41-71.
976 Boston, MA: Springer US.
- 977 Yuste R, Cossart R, Yaksi E (2024) Neuronal ensembles: Building blocks of neural circuits.
978 *Neuron* 112:875-892.
- 979 Zwick WR, Velicer WF (1986) Comparison of five rules for determining the number of
980 components to retain. *Psychological Bulletin* 99:432-442.
- 981